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Advancing Regenerative Sustainability with Wood Science

**JUNE 30 – JULY 5, 2024
GRAND HOTEL BERNARDIN
PORTOROŽ, SLOVENIA**

**Ilona Peszlen, President-Elect
Angela Haney, Executive Director**

Edited by Jeffrey Morrell

On behalf of the Society, I would like to thank all of those who attended the meeting and presented their research. I'd especially like to thank all of the students who attended and hope that they join us at future meetings.

Finally, I'd like to thank our Executive Director, Angela Haney, for organizing an excellent meeting and Jeff Morrell for assembling these proceedings. We hope you find them useful and look forward to seeing you all June 15-20, 2025, in Fort Collins, Colorado for our 68th Annual meeting.

Ilona Peszlen, SWST President

A prospect of engineered living materials in the building sector

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ABSTRACT

Materials have defined civilizations and their development. The relevance of a material today is a combination of its purpose, properties, availability, cost, manufacture, safety, and environmental impact. The new development of material science and the shift toward resilient and active systems requires responsible research and innovation that should guide technology development. The current legislation forces new research and business models that promote circularity, reuse of buildings and materials, whole life cycle thinking, high-performance operations, and ultimately a shift away from fossil fuels. The built environment can reduce emissions by selecting non-toxic building materials and products to support the health of inhabitants and the local ecosystem.

Bio-based materials represent a promising alternative for the building sector. They have the advantage of being renewable, possessing low embodied energy, and CO₂ neutral or even negative. However, the future of materials research lies in creative design that allows re-imagining the structure of materials and using their form to serve a certain purpose. Engineered living materials (ELMs) represent the subsequent advancements in materials science and engineering. ELMs use an alternative (living) set of building blocks compared with conventional man-made materials, allowing them to perform tasks associated with living systems such as self-replication, self-healing, or self-regulation.

This talk will present an overview of the prospect of ELMs in the building sector and provide the first results of the ARCHI-SKIN project that develops a living coating system for building facades.

Keywords: engineered living materials, bioinspired design, building sector, material science, multifunctionality

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